

Tin(IV) Complexes of Schiff Bases Derived from Salicylaldehyde or *O*-hydroxyacetophenone

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Hexacoordinated $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot (\text{SBH})_2$ type of derivatives have been synthesized by the 1:2 molar reactions of SnCl_4 with the Schiff bases, $\text{HO}C_6H_4\text{CH}:\text{NR}$ and $\text{HO}C_6H_4\text{C}(\text{CH}_3):\text{NR}'$ (where $\text{R}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; C_6H_7^+ or C_6H_9^+ and $\text{R}'=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$, C_6H_7^+ or C_6H_9^+). These behave as non-electrolytes in dimethylformamide. The coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the tin atom has been inferred by the upward shift of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ frequency with respect to the ligand spectra.

A few derivatives of tin(IV) chloride with the Schiff bases have been described in the literature¹⁻⁵.

In our earlier communications⁶⁻⁹ from these laboratories, reactions of tin(IV) chloride with the Schiff bases derived from the condensation of benzaldehyde, *o*-hydroxyacetophenone, pentane-2, 4-dione or salicylaldehyde with aminoalcohols have been reported and several new derivatives isolated for the first time. The reactions of tin(IV) chloride with the Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde or *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and amines have not, however, been studied so far. In the present paper, we wish to report the preparation and properties of tin(IV) complexes with Schiff bases obtained by the condensation of salicylaldehyde with ethylamine, *n*-propylamine and *n*-butylamine and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone with aniline, *n*-propylamine and *n*-butylamine.

Experimental

The reactions were carried out strictly in anhydrous conditions. Benzene(BDH) was first

refluxed over sodium wire for several hours and then distilled azeotropically with ethanol. Tin(IV) chloride (Reidel) was kept over copper turnings and redistilled before use. Dimethylformamide (BDH) was purified as described earlier⁶ and the middle fraction boiling at $55 \pm 1^\circ/35$ mm was collected and stored in blackened and stoppered pyrex flasks. The specific conductivity of the solvent was found to be $0.5 - 1.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Preparation of Schiff Bases

Schiff bases of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone or salicylaldehyde were prepared by mixing *o*-hydroxyacetophenone or salicylaldehyde and the amines in the equimolar ratio in benzene and refluxing for several hours, followed by the removal of water-benzene azeotrope. These were distilled before use. Their analyses and physical characteristics are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL PROPERTIES AND ANALYSES OF THE SCHIFF BASES

Sl. No.	Schiff base	State and m.p. (°C)	b.p. (°C/mm)	Analysis(%)		
				C Found (Calcd)	H Found (Calcd)	N Found (Calcd)
1.	Salicylidene ethylamine ($\text{C}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$)	Deep yellow liquid	63-64/0.1	72.12 (72.46)	7.25 (7.43)	9.18 (9.36)
2.	Salicylidene-1-propylamine ($\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}$)	Deep yellow liquid	90-91/1.0	73.47 (73.58)	7.96 (8.03)	8.49 (8.59)
3.	Salicylidene-1-butylamine ($\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$)	Deep yellow liquid	84/0.1	74.39 (74.57)	8.35 (8.47)	7.82 (7.91)
4.	<i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenoneanil ($\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}$)	Yellow solid 79-80	125/0.1	79.45 (79.62)	6.01 (6.21)	6.45 (6.63)
5.	<i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenone- <i>n</i> -propylamine ($\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}$)*	Yellow solid 45-46	140/4.0	74.29 (74.57)	8.21 (8.47)	7.78 (7.91)
6.	<i>o</i> -hydroxyacetophenone- <i>n</i> -butylamine ($\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$)	Yellow solid 65-66	110/0.4	75.25 (75.41)	8.78 (8.90)	7.21 (7.33)

*Has been used to distinguish between the compounds of same molecular formula.

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Preparation of Tin(IV) Complexes

Tin(IV) chloride was dissolved in benzene and a calculated amount of the Schiff base was then slowly added with constant shaking in the molar ratio of 1 : 2. In those cases, where the Schiff base was found to be insoluble in cold benzene, it was first dissolved by refluxing and then the solution was cooled. An exothermic reaction took place and the solid compound separated out immediately. After decanting off the solvent, the resulting solids were repeatedly washed with benzene and then dried at 40° at reduced pressure 0.5–1 mm of Hg for 1-2 hours. The resulting derivatives are insoluble in most of the common organic solvents but soluble in DMF. The details of their analyses, physical properties and molar conductance are given in Table 2.

indicating that these derivatives behave as non-electrolytes in DMF.

Coordination of the azomethine nitrogen to the tin atom is probably indicated by the shift of $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ frequency towards higher side^{1,5-7}. In the I.R. spectra of Schiff bases, strong band due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ appears at $\sim 1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the aldimines and $\sim 1625\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ketimines, whereas in the tin complexes this band is observed at $\sim 1645\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1640\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

If only the nitrogen of the azomethine group may coordinate then in the 1 : 1 complexes the metal atom will be pentacoordinated. However, the non-formation of 1 : 1 complexes probably indicates the unstable nature of the pentacoordination

TABLE 2—SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERISTICS OF TIN(IV) SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Tin tetra-chloride (g)	Schiff base (g)	Molar ratio	Compound, yield (g), nature	Analysis (%)		
					Sn Found (Calcd)	Cl Found (Calcd)	N Found (Calcd)
1.	1.35	C ₉ H ₁₁ NO 1.54	1 : 2	SnCl ₄ (C ₉ H ₁₁ NO) ₂ (2.83), yellow solid	21.94 (21.25)	25.61 (25.42)	4.89 (5.01)
2.	1.77	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ NO 2.21	1 : 2	SnCl ₄ (C ₁₀ H ₁₃ NO) ₂ (3.90), yellow solid	20.11 (20.23)	24.90 (24.20)	4.48 (4.77)
3.	1.80	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO 2.40	1 : 2	SnCl ₄ (C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO) ₂ (4.20), yellow solid	19.54 (19.32)	23.26 (23.10)	4.43 (4.55)
4.	1.00	C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO 1.63	1 : 2	SnCl ₄ (C ₁₄ H ₁₉ NO) ₂ (2.63), yellow solid	17.32 (17.39)	21.12 (20.80)	3.89 (4.10)
5.	0.55	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO* 0.74	1 : 2	SnCl ₄ (C ₁₁ H ₁₅ NO) ₂ * (1.16), white solid	18.97 (19.32)	23.56 (23.10)	4.43 (4.55)
6.	1.53	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NO 2.25	1 : 2	SnCl ₄ (C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NO) ₂ (3.78), white solid	17.88 (18.47)	21.95 (22.10)	4.15 (4.35)

Analytical Methods and Physical Measurements

Tin was estimated gravimetrically as tin oxide. Chlorine was determined as silver chloride and nitrogen by the Kjeldahl's method.

Conductance measurements were made using a Tesla RLC bridge with a cell having cell constant, 0.74 cm⁻¹. The infrared spectra of the ligands and complexes were recorded in nujol mulls on Perkin-Elmer 337 Grating I.R. Spectrophotometer in the range, 4000-700 cm⁻¹.

Results and Discussion

In these reactions, SnCl₄(SBH)₂ type of complexes could only be isolated. Even 1 : 1 and other molar ratio reactions were found to yield similar type of derivatives. Their limited solubilities in common organic solvents, however, did not permit the determination of their molecular weights. The molar conductance values as determined in DMF at 10⁻³M concentration and 25 ± 1° fall in the range 8.13–8.31 ohm⁻² cm² mol⁻²

state for the tin atom as reported earlier also^{1,5,10}. The non-coordinating nature of the phenolic OH group has also been reported in the complexes of tin(IV) chloride with salicylaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and only 1 : 2 complexes have been isolated¹¹.

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